
COUNCIL ON
LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
THIRTY-THIRD
ANNUAL REPORT/1989

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The scholar at his book-wheel is a reproduction of an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine . . .* Paris, 1588. It first appeared in the Council's third annual report, with the following explanation: "the picture symbolizes the interest of the Council on Library Resources in both the content of books and the mechanics of library service." The engraving has appeared in each annual report since that time.

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Contents

4	Members of the Council and of the Board of Directors
5	Committees and Officers
6	Staff and Consultants
7	Introduction
9	Program Review
10	CLR in 1989
12	Library Management and Operations
19	Librarianship and Professional Education
19	Continuing Education and Professional Support Programs
24	Information Studies: A New CLR Professional Education Program
33	Program Committees and Project Participants
36	Publications and Reports Resulting from CLR Programs, 1988/1989
40	Administrative Notes
42	Program Guidelines and Grant Application Procedures
45	Active Projects and Financial Statements, 1988/1989
46	Grants & Contracts Active in Fiscal 1989
57	Report of Independent Accountants and Financial Statements
65	Index

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1. Mr. Likins, Mr. Stuart-Stubbs, and Mr. Verba were elected to the Board at the May 1989 Directors' meeting.

2. Resigned, November 1988.

3. Mr. Hubbard succeeded Mr. Liebaers in FY 1989.

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4. Resigned, June 1989.

Introduction

This, the thirty-third *Annual Report* of the Council on Library Resources, includes a review of activities for 1988/89, the rosters of the committees that have assisted CLR, a list of publications and reports that have grown out of CLR programs and grants, an account of administrative matters of general interest, a record of currently active grants, and, finally, the audited financial reports for the year.

As full as the report is with facts and figures, it is still only an indicator of what CLR and those institutions and individuals receiving grant support believe to be the current and most important issues for libraries and librarianship. At best, this report is an outline of the work of a single year, and readers are invited to inquire about any of the topics covered or to comment on what we are seeking to do.

PROGRAM REVIEW

CLR in 1989

We are told with some frequency that, even after thirty-three years, CLR is still useful and still needed. Why is this so? After all, the world of libraries is much changed in size and character from what it was in 1956. The number and size of research libraries are far greater; new support and service organizations have come into being; and thousands of librarians, information scientists, archivists, and other specialists are hard at work dealing with complex operating problems, looking for ways to improve performance, seeking to respond to needs and expectations that rise far faster than resources, and, all the while, installing a steady stream of new technologies without jeopardizing collecting goals or present capabilities. There are still many difficulties—there always are—but the recent record of libraries is, by and large, one of remarkable accomplishment.

Given such progress and the pace of the present, where does CLR fit in and what does it contribute to the cause of shaping a productive and humane information age? The annual task of preparing a review of program activities provides an opportunity to answer that question, since what we do is what we are.

First, we are detached. That doesn't mean we work without purpose, but it does mean that, because we have no institution to protect, we can explore widely and with fewer constraints than many others. And the many individuals who help with those explorations seem to welcome the opportunity to put aside their own duties for a time, to join with colleagues in considering important matters when the opening line is "what if?"

Second, we are a small undertaking, and can respond both quickly and carefully to proposals that fall within the scope of our program interests. Further, we try not to be rigid in defining those interests so that we can occasionally help out in exceptional situations.

Third, we have funds available, limited as they are, to assist individuals in an important group of professions in which opportunities for financial support are few and far between.

Fourth, as an operating foundation, we are able at times to take the initial steps required to get very large and very important projects under way. In some of these ventures, we fail—the National Periodicals Center comes to mind. But others have had a measure of success—the Bibliographic Service

Development Program and its Linked Systems Project is an example, as is the now-flourishing Commission on Preservation and Access. Professional education, a topic just now moving to center stage at CLR, may well become a future case study.

Finally, CLR—its board and staff—believe deeply in libraries, librarians, and all of the related institutions and professions that, together, make possible the use of the records of civilization and that continue to devise and establish ways to weave the web of information into a structure that serves many purposes in many ways. It is an ill-defined assignment but a real one, and, in terms of social importance, well worth pursuing. This is why CLR, with its many allies, is still useful and still needed.

Library Management and Operations

During the past five years, the Council has sponsored a wide-ranging program of research and analysis concerning all aspects of library operations. The members of the Research Library Committee serve as both stimulants for and assessors of CLR projects undertaken and grants made in the context of this program. The broad purpose is to consider the future form of research libraries, which has meant concentrating on strategic planning and management issues and on the principal elements of library responsibility—collections and their preservation, bibliographic services, and access. The number of specific topics that might be included in each of these rubrics is limitless, so we have sought both in CLR-managed projects and in the grants that have been made to pick those in which analysis and demonstration would be especially informative or would open up new and potentially influential opportunities.

It is relatively easy to record CLR activities and the work done by others with CLR funds that, in one way or another, are intended to improve some aspect of operating performance or the overall management of libraries. But what CLR can do each year is a very small part of a very large, and often implicit, library agenda. Bibliographic processes and products, equitable access to information, cost containment, collection strength and integrity, effective cooperation among libraries, adoption of promising technologies, the integration of library functions with research and teaching, and purposeful management that meets established obligations in a dynamic environment are all matters that require continuing attention.

The agenda, demanding as it is, is also an expanding one and is well beyond the capabilities of any given organization. Fortunately, a primary asset of the library community is the large and growing number of organizations that are assuming responsibility for segments of the work—OCLC, the Research Libraries Group, the Association of Research Libraries, the Commission on Preservation and Access, the national libraries, federal and state agencies, professional associations, commercial vendors of library systems and databases, paper manufacturers, and the scholarly publishing community are only some of those involved. Given such diversity, the greatest challenge for the library world is maintaining a sense of purpose and reasonable order so that the well-being of an international, information-dependent society is as carefully protected as the involved organizations.

It is, perhaps, in this arena of establishing links that CLR is coming to find its present place. A review of grants and CLR-managed projects for the past year produces a long list, but the foundation for that work has been many hours of discussions and meetings involving individuals from almost every concerned group and involved organization.

The Research Library Committee, with its membership drawn from key disciplines in the humanities and social sciences and the ranks of university and library administrators, serves as a forum actively considering the principal topics pertinent to scholarly communication and the future services of research libraries and archives. The Linked Systems Project Policy Committee and subcommittees for applications and technical issues involve executives of networks, representatives of the Library of Congress, librarians, and systems specialists from both library and commercial operations. The Bibliographic Services Study Committee, which is charged both with assessing the National Coordinated Cataloging Program experiment and with speculating about the future form of bibliographic services, brings together library administrative officers who are especially knowledgeable in bibliographic matters. The Commission on Preservation and Access, now an independent agency but still funded in part by CLR, has carefully enlisted help in its deliberations from every concerned quarter. The Foundation Library Committee, which has met periodically for more than ten years, keeps interested foundations in touch with a wide range of library developments. The roll is not complete, but it serves to make the point that the CLR offices are often a meeting ground, and much of the time of CLR staff is dedicated to bringing people together.

Such discussions lead to action of many kinds. What follows is a status report on several long-term projects and a record of activities funded in 1988/89 that relate directly to the key components of the CLR Program on Library Management and Operations.

Planning and Management

Four multi-year, complementary projects have been funded in the context of the research program, each of them designed to contribute to understanding better the projected needs and expectations for future library services and to explore alternative strategic planning methods.

The most ambitious of these projects, begun in 1986, is nearing completion at UCLA, where Robert Hayes has explored Long-Range Strategic Planning for Libraries and Information Resources in the Research University. The project will be completed by December 31, 1989, and an invitational conference will be held under the auspices of the Research Library Committee to consider the results and other, related, issues. It is expected that an extensive report will be made available during 1990.

At the University of Minnesota, a project team with members drawn from the University Libraries, the Humphrey Institute of Public Affairs, and the Carlson School of Management collaborated during 1987/88 on designing a working model for an integrated information center (IIC) for the Humphrey

Institute. Five project components involved assessments of information requirements, information technology, organizational structure, funding and recovery of costs, and legal and policy issues. Alternative configurations of a model IIC were developed and have been reviewed internally; implementation is under consideration. A summary of the extensive project report is available from the Council.

At the University of Illinois at Chicago, library staff members worked during a two-year period with members of the University's Institute for the Humanities to learn more of present and projected needs of scholars. The project ended with an invitational symposium, "Humanists at Work," held April 27–28, 1989. The University plans to publish the papers.

The newest project in this group, one that began early in 1989, is designed to extend the work of the Laboratory for Applied Research in Academic Information of the Welch Medical Library (The Johns Hopkins University) to fields beyond medicine. CLR has provided funding that will enable the Welch Library to (1) strengthen its research activities related to full-text knowledge management by including a human factors component, (2) expand the development and field-testing of present dynamic text experiments in human genetics and ambulatory medicine to other scholarly fields and disciplines, and (3) develop a professional training program in knowledge management, beginning with continuing education seminars and summer institutes. The work funded by CLR will continue into 1992.

In addition, a special project undertaken by CLR at the request of the National Science Foundation (NSF) began as the year ended. CLR has agreed to explore on behalf of NSF the relationship between the information structure for science and engineering and the level of research activity and progress in those disciplines. An invitational conference on this subject is planned for October 1989 and, subsequently, a series of papers will be commissioned on specific topics for use by NSF staff in preparing an expanded section for the biennial NSF publication, *Science and Engineering Indicators*. This effort complements in many ways the work of the Research Library Committee, which concentrates on the interests of scholars in the humanities and the social sciences.

Grants made during 1988/89 related to planning and library management include the following:

Association of Research Libraries

To expand the analytical and interpretive sections of the 1989 Automation Inventory.

Association of Research Libraries

To complete a study of serial costs and to develop and implement strategies for reducing the rate of increase of serial prices.

Harvard University

To provide partial funding for a symposium on "Music Librarianship in America" in the fall of 1989.

Harvard University

To study the modes of delivery to library patrons of information in electronic formats.

Johns Hopkins University

To create a knowledge management program through the Laboratory for Applied Research in Academic Information, a unit of the Welch Medical Library.

Stanford University

To study the causes of increases in subscription prices, the proliferation of scholarly journals, and the economic and technological factors that influence costs (joint support with the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation).

University of Illinois at Chicago

For librarian assistance in a study of humanists' use of libraries.

University of Wisconsin-Madison

To hold a symposium entitled "The 21st Century and the Future of the Book" at Knox College in the spring of 1989.

Yale University

To train self-managing teams within the Technical Services division at Yale University Library as part of a reorganization effort.

Resources and Preservation

The Commission on Preservation and Access has taken the lead in preservation matters, and works to encourage and assist preservation activities in many settings, nationally and internationally, but the long-standing CLR interest in assuring the protection and integrity of library collections is still evidenced by its financial support for the Commission and occasional grants for specific projects.

Brigham Young University

To create a prototype non-damaging book return unit.

Commission on Preservation and Access

For operating support.

Franklin & Marshall College

To test the results of a research project involving the application of a preservation typology to a subject collection in the College's library, while providing preservation training to other liberal arts college librarians.

Library of Congress

To provide partial support for a national conference on the development of state preservation programs, cosponsored by the Library of Congress, the National Endowment for the Humanities, and a number of other organizations.

Mid-Atlantic Preservation Service

To fund a meeting to evaluate the Mid-Atlantic Preservation Service's building program.

New York Public Library

To help cover the cost of operating the Paper Permanency Program in The Research Libraries.

Bibliographic Services

Cataloging and bibliography—the organization of information—are the threads that link all library activities. As such, it is no surprise that these topics have been a part of CLR's program from the beginning. The cause of bibliography was at the heart of the Linked Systems Project (LSP) that dominated Council funds and staff for much of the 1980s. The success of that work and, more important, the acceptance of the principle of equitable access to bibliographic records reflect real progress, though neither objective is as yet fully realized. But the work goes forward under the general guidance of the LSP Policy Committee and the more direct work of the two subcommittees, Technology and Bibliographic Applications (committee members are listed on pages 33 and 34).

A second CLR-sponsored group, the Bibliographic Services Study Committee (BSSC), has a dual assignment. First, it is charged with assessing the costs and performance of the experimental National Coordinated Cataloging Program being coordinated by the Library of Congress. That work and the Committee's report should be completed by mid-1990. A second BSSC assignment is to consider future bibliographic requirements and cataloging practices in the context of costs, needs, and organizational capabilities. While the subject is one that requires continuing attention in many quarters, it is the Committee's plan to bring at least the first phase of its work to a conclusion and to prepare the way for wide discussion of the topic during the next year (BSSC members are listed on page 33).

In addition to these CLR-managed activities, several grants were made during the year for bibliographic projects.

Indiana University of Pennsylvania

To develop a computer-based system for browsing online public access catalogs that will provide better subject access to the collections.

Museum Computer Network

To investigate the feasibility of using MARC formats for cataloging art objects.

University of Kentucky

To assist Lois M. Chan in completing a revision of the *Guide to the Library of Congress Classification*.

University of Toronto

To study the interaction of information retrieval systems and types of users.

Access

Providing equitable access to recorded information has been an underlying purpose of most library activities since libraries themselves were established as publicly supported agencies. The principle is implicit not only for public libraries but for the research libraries that are an integral part of higher education, research, and scholarship, which can flourish only with full and unrestricted access to information.

But in recent times, adherence to the principle of equitable access has been increasingly difficult. The reasons are many—the sheer quantity of useful information now produced worldwide is almost overwhelming, and the rate of increase shows no signs of slowing; new information formats (e.g., online databases, CD-ROM) require an electronic interface and, often, specialized training; legal issues related to copyright and the ownership of intellectual property in the new technological setting are largely unresolved; rising information costs impede access for economic reasons; and neither public nor institutional information policies have kept pace with the rapid change in all aspects of the information structure.

Growing concerns about such matters induced CLR to give new emphasis to the objective of equitable access to information, both for its own program operation and as an influence on a wide range of national and international activities concerned with the work of libraries, archives, and other information-based institutions. Ford Foundation funding helped CLR pursue this objective, directly and indirectly, for several years and evidence is strong that the concept of equitable access to information is now established as a primary specification, not only for current operations but for the future form of libraries.

Many of the problems have not been resolved, but in almost every important segment of library activity the principle of equitable access to information is explicitly acknowledged and the importance of the matter has pene-

trated the planning activities of many institutions and organizations. In essence, access has become a visible byword for the work of public and academic libraries alike.

In the context of CLR's program, it became obvious that the general topic of access to information could not be isolated and attended to as a discrete matter. Each year's experience underscored how interconnected the matter of access was to all program areas. As a result, CLR has sought to integrate the concept into all Council efforts, whether related to preservation, bibliographic services, planning and management, or professional and continuing education.

Many of the grants made in the CLR Fellows Program and the Cooperative Research Program, described elsewhere in this report, dealt with topics related to information access. In addition, several grants were made in support of this central cause.

The Bridge to China Foundation

To provide partial support for a book drive on behalf of Chinese universities, to be undertaken in California by the American Association of University Women.

National Commission on Libraries and Information Science

To provide partial support for an invitational conference on information literacy, cosponsored by NCLIS and the American Association of School Librarians.

University of Wisconsin-Madison

To modify a reference evaluation software system, making the program available to public libraries.

* * * * *

The foregoing summary of the year's work reinforces the validity of continuing CLR concentration on library management and gives at least a hint of the effort required to deal with the operating and service complexities that librarians face. What an annual report cannot do is to record the effect of this effort and expenditure on library services and capabilities. In the end, that is an evaluation that can be made only in each library, because much of the influence of research, thoughtful discussion, and demonstration is determined by the ways individual libraries and librarians translate what is known and learned into their operating situations. The assessment of results is more the work of historians than it is of report writers.

Librarianship and Professional Education

While CLR has, since 1956, concentrated on improving library operations and management, serious attention to the needs of the profession itself developed somewhat later. But once this subject found its place on CLR's agenda during the 1970s, it moved steadily ahead; today librarians share equal billing with the more impersonal world of technologies and systems. The reasons are obvious. As the information structure that undergirds research and scholarship—and, for that matter, most social enterprises—becomes more complex and costly, the individuals who are obligated to make that structure work well need a new and extensive set of capabilities and a sophisticated understanding of the information requirements of a diverse and constantly expanding population. All members of the profession are being affected by these new requirements, from the quality of their basic professional education and the development of specialized skills to their ability to conduct pertinent and influential research on the full range of questions inherent in the new information age.

CLR gradually has expanded support for continuing education with a series of grant programs, each one designed to meet the needs of individuals with specific interests and requirements. Those programs and 1988/89 participants are recorded below. Professional education itself, and the research foundation on which it rests, is also a topic of great importance, and CLR has been trying to find where it might be of help. The way we intend to begin is outlined toward the end of this report. It will be clear to readers that this is possibly the Council's most demanding undertaking yet.

Continuing Education and Professional Support Programs

Late in August 1988, CLR convened a group of eighteen senior library officers from across the country to review the Council's continuing education efforts and to assess proposed additions to the program. That meeting, and a series of subsequent discussions with additional individuals from academic and public libraries, underscored the importance to the profession of com-

petitive and rigorous continuing education efforts of the kinds the Council manages or supports, and endorsed additional undertakings of several types.

As a result, an increasing portion of the Council's financial and personnel resources are being invested in a set of competitive programs that are designed to provide financial support for individuals to conduct research and undertake analytical studies on topics of interest or to enable exceptional individuals at all levels of professional experience to extend their knowledge and skills. The number of these programs is expanding as funds become available and, simultaneously, the level of participation is increasing.

A new program supporting international librarianship and a special course for archivists were added to the list during the year, and additional activities are under consideration.

CLR Fellows

This competitive program offers financial support to professional staff members of academic, research, and public libraries who wish to undertake research or conduct analytical studies pertinent to library operations and services or to pursue other professional projects of importance. Grants made during 1988/89 include:

Marianna Tax Choldin, C. Walter and Gerda Mortenson Distinguished Professor for International Library Programs and Director, Russian and East European Center, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, to study the Soviet practice of censoring via translation.

Ling Hwey Jeng, Assistant Professor, College of Library and Information Services, University of Maryland, to design a database management system for cataloging rules. The title of her project is "Anglo-American Cataloging Rules as a Knowledge Base: A Pilot Study."

Janet Sims-Wood, Reference Librarian and Afro-American History Specialist of the Moorland-Spingarn Research Center, Howard University, to complete *Mary McLeod Bethune: An Annotated Bibliography with Personal Recollections*.

Richard Hume Werking, Director of Libraries, Trinity University, for a study of "Collection Growth and Automation in Academic Libraries: Recent History and Current Patterns," in which he is examining the interplay between collection growth and automation since 1960, comparing the experience in college libraries with data from research libraries.

Academic Library Management Intern Program

Three interns spent the 1988/89 academic year with host library directors, bringing to fifty the number of CLR interns selected and supported during

the past fifteen years. The Council plans to offer internships for the 1990/91 academic year; the application process is already under way. Selection will be completed by March 1990.

The 1988/89 interns were:

Patricia Iannuzzi, who worked with Joseph Rosenthal, director, University Library, University of California, Berkeley;

Sarah M. Pritchard, who worked with Donald Koepp, university librarian, Princeton University; and

Sarah B. Watstein, who worked with Norman Stevens, director, University of Connecticut Library.

Cooperative Research Grants

This program is designed to stimulate productive communication between librarians and faculty members, to encourage librarians to develop more fully their research skills, and to increase the quantity and quality of library-related research. Grants made to librarian-faculty teams fund direct costs incurred in the conduct of the research project. Many of the projects funded in past years have resulted in publications.

Cooperative Research grants made during 1988/89 include:

Jean Currie, Linda Stewart, and Paul Yarbrough, Cornell University

To create a scholarly information system making bibliographic, numeric, and full-text electronic information sources available to scholars in their offices and laboratories.

Cheryl Elzy and Alan Nourie, Illinois State University, and Wilfrid Lancaster, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

To carry out unobtrusive evaluation of reference services.

Larry Hardesty, Eckerd College, and David Kaser, Indiana University

To examine the attitudes of principal academic officers in selective American colleges toward their institutions' libraries.

Shelley A. Bader and Thomas E. Piemme, George Washington University

To investigate the selection and utilization of four MEDLINE search systems by faculty and medical residents.

Bert Boyce, Louisiana State University, and Judith Boyce, State Library of Louisiana

To collect and analyze literature on the subject of bookmobiles to provide an overall picture of the place of bookmobile service in improving access to public library collections.

Janet Edgerton and Raymond Taylor, North Carolina State University

To study the editing efficiency of a large, online bibliographic information system, based on an examination of a comprehensive file of edit commands.

Alison Scott Ricker and Jeffrey Witmer, Oberlin College

To conduct a survey of liberal arts college libraries to document the support they provide for research and education in the sciences.

Hendrik Edelman and Myoung Chung Wilson, Rutgers University

To study the impact of interdisciplinary research on library collection building.

David Crookall and Larry Harbin, University of Alabama

To carry out a pilot study investigating the complex procedures involved in setting up a fully operational database on simulation/gaming.

Sheila Bertram and Merrill Distad, University of Alberta

To design a program, based on a newly created serials database, for regional resource sharing of core scientific, technical, and medical serials for the university libraries of the western Canadian provinces.

Nancy Van House and Beth Weil, University of California, Berkeley

To test the methods and instruments for data collection in several different academic libraries, employing user surveys that have been developed for a manual of output measures in academic libraries.

Dale Montanelli and Joy Pottboff, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

To test the application of behavioral research methodology to environmental design problems in libraries.

Mark Pfeifer and Gwendolyn Snodgrass, University of Louisville

To evaluate the methods currently used by medical school libraries to deal with invalid or retracted literature, and to suggest ways to enhance awareness and decrease utilization of invalid material.

Delia Neuman and Rebecca Van Campen, University of Maryland

To develop an instructional computer program to help students make more effective use of the periodical literature.

Edward Fox and Linda Wilson, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University

To compare methods for providing access to large online catalogs by analyzing questionnaire and logging data from two hundred participants using four approaches to gaining access to the online catalog.

Senior Fellows

More than thirty representatives from the first four classes of UCLA Senior Fellows met with CLR staff and members of the Research Library Committee in August 1988 to consider future characteristics of academic research libraries and to discuss the changes required to enable libraries to meet anticipated new service responsibilities. The report of the meeting has served to expand the scope of topics being considered by the Council's Research Library Committee, and the discussion itself reflected the quality of the Senior Fellows and the breadth of their professional concerns and competence.

CLR will again provide partial support for the Senior Fellows seminar, which is managed by the Graduate School of Library and Information Science at the University of California, Los Angeles. The fifth class of Senior Fellows, as listed below, will convene at UCLA during August 1989.

Elaine Albright, University of Maine
 Rachael Anderson, Columbia University
 Alison Bunting, University of California, Los Angeles
 Mary Horres, University of California, San Diego
 Edward Johnson, Oklahoma State University
 Robert Patterson, University of Tulsa
 Shelley Phipps, University of Arizona
 Marion Reid, Louisiana State University
 Donald Riggs, Arizona State University
 Jane Robbins, University of Wisconsin, Madison
 Sherrie Schmidt, Texas A&M University
 Helen Spaulding, University of Missouri-Kansas City
 Richard Werking, Trinity University
 Florence Wilson, Peabody College
 Karin Wittenborg, University of California, Los Angeles

Robert Vosper IFLA Fellows

The Council has provided funding for use over three years to establish a fellowship program administered by the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, with awards to be made on a competitive basis to outstanding librarians with an interest in and a commitment to the international aspects of library service. The fellowships have been named to honor Robert Vosper, CLR Board member, in recognition of his long and effective contribution to the cause of international librarianship. Recipients of the first four IFLA Fellowships are:

Mark Roosa, University of Delaware, U.S.A.
 Laine Ruus, University of Toronto, Canada
 Joanna Wellheiser, Metropolitan Toronto Reference Library, Canada
 Marc Walckiers, Université de Louvain, Belgium

Institute for Government Archivists

A grant was made to the University of Pittsburgh's School of Library and Information Science to conduct an institute for government archivists on the archival management of electronic information. The first two-week session for individuals from state archives and the National Archives and Records Administration was held during June 1989. A brief winter meeting of participants and a second two-week session in June of 1990 will complete the program.

Other CLR grants made in 1988/89 to support library education include:

Simmons College

To help publish the second volume of proceedings of the Symposium on Recruiting, Educating, and Training Cataloging Librarians.

University of Alabama

To allow Margaret F. Stieg to prepare a book on library education, to be published by the American Library Association.

Information Studies: A New CLR Professional Education Program

Note: This section of the 1988/89 *Annual Report* describes in broad outline a new CLR program that is designed to strengthen professional education for librarianship by encouraging productive collaboration among leading library schools, by expanding the scope and increasing the importance and influence of research in information studies, and by improving ties between the profession and the education and research activities on which the profession depends. It is the intent of CLR to encourage the discussion and support the action that is required to accomplish these objectives. The program, which will take shape over time, has evolved from past CLR activities undertaken on behalf of professional education; its general thrust has been developed with help from librarians, library educators, and the members of the CLR Board.

The Council on Library Resources has sponsored many discussions about the state of the information professions and, more specifically, about professional education for careers in librarianship, information science, and archival management. There is widespread agreement among those who have taken part that these closely related fields (here they are treated as one), all of them concerned with assembling and providing access both to specified current information and to the accumulated records of civilization, are in a period of fundamental change and that librarians and archivists are dealing with new,

complex, and difficult problems that need careful attention. Because its work is demanding and of great importance, the profession requires now, more than ever before, an educational foundation that fully reflects the long-established obligations that are touchstones for both libraries and archives as well as the new demands implicit in a technology-driven future and a rapidly changing operational setting.

The recent history of libraries has been one of remarkable achievement; over two decades they have—individually and collectively—led a bibliographic revolution. Computerized catalogs and telecommunication links now enable users to identify published information regardless of its location and, increasingly, to gain access promptly to needed items. New organizations have been developed to deal with such shared concerns as the preservation of library collections, recognized today as a public problem of fundamental importance. Improved management and cooperation have greatly reduced unit costs for technical services, and libraries are now engaged in assessing the effects of new text storage technologies on operations and services.

The scope of recent change is the strongest indicator of the dimension of an information revolution that is still in its infancy. The rapidity with which it has come has pressed hard both library personnel and financial resources and has fostered a transformation (some would say a distortion) of collecting practices and service capabilities. It is certainly clear that the perception of what a library is and needs to be has changed for all time. The effort of recent years, while primarily concentrated on computer applications to library operations, has also generated new user expectations, created additional costs, raised organizational issues, and highlighted complex policy questions. Further, and because of the effect across the entire information arena of the same technologies, libraries are operating in a dramatically changed setting, nationally and internationally.

The profession is aware that the future is not simply an extension of the past, and educators, especially in the leading schools, have recently added in important ways to traditional educational programs. But it is increasingly obvious that present realities are passing by existing educational capabilities. Despite much work and some constructive change, notably in certain specialized fields, the profession and its educators have not yet come together on a comprehensive plan of action to address either the fundamental problems or the projected needs of the profession. In part, this failure stems from the fact that subsets of the profession (e.g., research university librarians, public librarians, government archivists, corporate information officers) are, for practical purposes, self-contained groups with discrete interests and needs, while library schools, as they must, view their market generically. Taken as a whole, the profession has had difficulty establishing, internally, an understanding of the full range of its responsibilities and articulating its educational requirements.

Because the discussion has seldom risen above immediate and sometimes parochial interests, a false dichotomy has developed, too simply characterized

as “theory” versus “practice.” The profession was founded on a base of methodology, and the emphasis on “practical matters” has been dominant ever since. Even in today’s electronic setting, technique remains the primary educational theme. But as librarians have been faced with the new and important questions that have come with the information age, it has become apparent that the educational and operational focus on procedures is no longer adequate. There are many complex issues that require continuing attention, the answers to which will affect not just library operations but, because they are central to the future form of our information system, the nature of education and the course of society itself. No dynamic profession can rest only on a foundation of methodology.

At the heart of many of the present problems facing librarians and library education is the failure to describe the profession and its present role in terms that are compelling, expansive, and accurate. The principles, the responsibilities, and the body of knowledge that shape the profession are real and of great importance to every component of society, but they are either largely implicit or incompletely formed, and are certainly not widely understood. Further, because the province of libraries and archives—that is, the human record itself—is unbounded, it is difficult to move from simple generalizations to specific and unambiguous examples of the relevance of that record to every endeavor. The profession rests more on assumptions of worth than on demonstrable and accepted fact. This is not an adequate base for future performance. It is time to explore, understand, and make better known the substantive foundations of the profession. Until this is done, every aspect of the profession and of professional education will be handicapped.

The key issues

A long list of matters for attention could be derived from recent reviews of the state of librarianship and library education, but on careful analysis most such items are only symptoms of a small set of underlying problems that affect all aspects of the profession—both operations and education. It is these matters that most need attention.

1. Ambiguity in the definition of “libraries” and “librarianship”

The recent modification in the designation of many library schools—insertion of the term “information science” in one way or another—is indicative of an attitude that assigns responsibility for past practices to librarians and aspirations for the future to a new and different breed. Extension of library school programs into pertinent new areas at times runs afoul of competing interests in business schools, computer science departments, schools of engineering, communication programs, and law schools. In universities, operating responsibility for information systems and services is frequently divided between libraries and computing centers; increasingly, the fragmentation is viewed as a bothersome problem to be solved administratively by superimposing a new position on what already exists. The failure to address the matters of

substance behind this ambiguity sets limits on the development of librarianship and curtails constructive change in the underlying educational structure.

2. The low visibility of librarianship and library professional education

Justified or not, the profession is handicapped by its image—tradition-bound, focused on internal operations, reactive rather than entrepreneurial, and having no clearly defined professional turf. Library schools, themselves, tend to be small in enrollment and faculty size, and have a marginal presence in the university. Salaries of librarians are low by most professional measures, thus constraining investment by individuals in their own basic and continuing professional education. For many of the same reasons, opportunities are limited for the wide-ranging and distinctive supplementary education that is essential for a profession seeking to cope in a rapidly changing and demanding new operational setting.

3. The shortage of first-rate candidates for faculty positions in library schools

Several deans, especially those new to their posts and those trying to strengthen their schools, report difficulty in identifying first-rate teachers who also have distinctive research and publication records and who would be viewed as fully credible academic appointments in the context of overall university standards and expectations for faculty. Further, it is exceptionally difficult to interest strong prospects from complementary disciplines to participate in library education.

4. The paucity of sound research on important topics and the lack of a significant research tradition on which to build

Even after acknowledging the production of useful analytical studies over the years and the contributions of some distinguished educators, the fact remains that much past and current research pertinent to today's information world does not meet in scope, quality, or influence reasonable expectations for such an important field. CLR, with funds available for research in several broad areas, has been handicapped by a shortage of proposals that fully justify support. Public and institutional policy questions, as distinct from technical topics, are of great importance but receive little rigorous attention. Measured against work done in other fields, accumulated research results do not provide a sufficient foundation for either professional education or library management to meet the requirements of a new era.

A proposal for action

The Council's 1988 Annual Report observed that CLR financial support for library schools to encourage experimentation, while important to some individual schools, had not stimulated fundamental improvement in professional

education. It was further noted that while, as for all academic enterprises, each school sets its own course, CLR might still find ways to be of assistance by making it possible for some of the leading schools to address their needs and the needs of the profession. **This, therefore, is a proposal for a collaborative effort to encourage exploration of the discipline of information studies and to stimulate research that will contribute to the improvement of practice and the quality of education for the field.**

Many needs have been identified by librarians and library educators; most stem from the fact that the critical mass of influential research that is required to give the discipline of information studies the depth and scope needed to provide a forceful academic presence has not yet been sufficiently developed. Until the discipline of information studies is fully established, understood, and acknowledged by the academic community as the foundation for the profession, both librarianship and library education will be handicapped. More important, society will be deprived of the sophisticated professional support that is necessary to make the benefits of the information age widely and fully accessible. It is this underlying problem that most requires attention.

The definition of information studies is itself not yet fully formed: clearly it is more than library science, more than information science. It is perhaps best seen as the study of the characteristics and organization of information; the effectiveness of the processes by which information is generated, distributed, and used; the relationship between information systems and users, including all factors affecting that relationship; and, finally, the functions and performance of the institutions and organizations charged with providing the systems and services required by individuals and society.

Engagement in information studies must be driven by the cause of satisfactory and equitable access to information, especially in support of teaching, learning, research, and scholarship. The need to understand the information process is essential in itself, but the effective utilization of what has been learned is now a matter of critical public concern.

Strengthening the disciplinary foundation of the profession is the key to recasting professional education itself. For this to happen, three steps are proposed.

- First, the strongest library schools should be encouraged to join forces to support intellectually, educationally, and even financially a long-term effort to create a cohesive and rigorous professional education program. These schools, in collaboration with professional leaders, must help set a new standard for academic expectations and show the way for the discipline as a whole.
- Second, a model research and advanced education program should be established to enrich the substance and expand the influence of information studies and, over time, to increase the quality and number of

candidates for library school faculty posts. This Center for Advanced Information Studies will provide an academic base for individuals from a number of disciplines who are working on topics pertinent to information studies and, ultimately, to library operations.

- Finally, an advisory and review capability must be created to provide a careful and continuing assessment of program progress and results. The CLR Committee on Information Studies, expanded to assure participation of individuals from the academic and research communities, the professions themselves, and the affected public, will be asked to assume this responsibility.

The undertaking proposed here is a difficult one but prospects are good given time, adequate financial support, necessary administrative assistance, and, most of all, the combined efforts of individuals from many fields, working with librarians, in a common cause. Success will foster durable and visible improvement in professional education and, over time, in the management and performance of libraries and all other organizations that share responsibility for keeping the human record.

I. The Information Studies Collaborative

Concentrating the strength of leading schools in a national program to establish information studies as a discrete discipline and to improve the quality and influence of professional education will require a formal collaborative organization. The form of that organization, its method of working, and the scope and limits of its program must be developed by the principals. As a first step, CLR will establish a small Working Committee to consider the structure and program of the collaborative. The Working Committee will not be expected to produce a definitive plan of action, but it will identify items for initial attention and propose ways to begin work. Among topics for the Committee's consideration:

1. Composition and management of the Collaborative

There is agreement among those who have been consulted that, initially, a few library schools must assume the responsibility for proposing steps to improve professional education. How will those schools be identified and enlisted? What should be the obligations and conditions for participation? How can the composition of the Collaborative assure that its work will be constructive and influential and not divisive? How can the profession itself be constructively involved in the work?

2. Collaborative activities

The agenda for the Collaborative will focus initially on matters that undergird the academic programs of all schools. The following list only

illustrates the range of topics that the Working Committee will need to consider in drafting the beginning agenda for the Collaborative.

- The nature of undergraduate preparation for a career in information studies.
- The need and specifications for professional internship programs.
- Recruiting to the field of information studies individuals with an active interest in an academic discipline and establishing special professional education programs to complement advanced training in a subject discipline.
- The instructional and research responsibilities of librarians.
- Library school faculty development programs.
- Preparation of a basic statement on the nature of professional education in information studies and consideration of a uniform degree.
- Enhancing the visibility of information studies as a career.

In addition to undertaking specific projects, the Information Studies Collaborative will also need to consider ways for schools to contribute to and benefit from the activities of the Center for Advanced Information Studies described below. This affiliation may include participation in a fellowship program, visiting faculty programs, and jointly sponsored conferences, seminar series, and publication ventures.

The principal objective of the Working Committee is to design the foundation for an influential, productive, visible, and evolving new organization that will capitalize on existing strengths and set the course for an intensive and productive period of action that will enhance the substance and influence of professional education in information studies.

Leading members of the profession and the most influential schools have, together, made good progress over the past two decades in upgrading library and information services. That very success has created new expectations and defined new horizons. But an underlying set of constraints—economic, organizational, and personnel—must be addressed if those expectations are to be met and the possibilities offered by information technology are to be put to fullest use. By the same token, the collections of libraries, the bibliographic keys to those collections, and the intellectual and historical continuity that libraries provide and protect must flourish as well. The responsibility to merge successfully the past with the future rests with the profession, and the ability of the profession is determined in large part by its educational base. The Information Studies Collaborative must take the lead; the results of its efforts will be measured over time by the performance of the profession in the decades ahead.

II. Center for Advanced Information Studies

A Center for Advanced Information Studies is proposed as the means to redefine, invigorate, and expand the academic foundation of information

studies. Such a Center, imaginatively organized, effectively led, and adequately funded, would provide an additional site and a nationally visible focus for research in information studies, concentrating especially on topics directly pertinent to library operations and services, questions relating information resources to the conduct of scholarship and the quality of teaching, and issues affecting the provision of satisfactory and equitable access to publications and information for all of society.

The program of the Center would be designed and administered so as to encourage participation of faculty and graduate students from many disciplines. This requirement suggests location in a major research university and a multidisciplinary organizational structure. In addition, through funded fellowships, individuals from other universities would be actively affiliated with the Center. Sponsored seminars and other appropriate means would be used to establish and maintain working relationships with librarians and faculty at other locations.

It is anticipated that the Center and certain library schools would join forces to assure that the participants in and the products of Center activity would promote the long-term development of professional education. The management of the Center would include university officers and faculty, but for purposes of program integration appropriate representation from the Information Studies Collaborative is required as well.

The details of the Center's research program will be governed by the interests of the involved faculty, but it is emphasized that the goal of the Center is to exert a powerful influence on the development of information studies as an important academic discipline. The existing CLR Research Program offers some insight into possible research areas, but the range of obvious topics is far greater. Simply put, and only as examples, there is great need to understand better

- how information can best be described, analyzed, integrated, and organized for use;
- how certain policies, set at all levels of government, affect access to information;
- the effect of technology-based information systems on scholarship, learning, government, and the public well-being;
- the economics of information;
- the effect of organizational structure on information diffusion; and
- the constraints on effecting change.

In summary, the Center for Advanced Information Studies would, in a purposeful way, explore information characteristics, information systems, and the organizational structures dedicated to assuring the protection of and access to the human record. Research results should promote improvement in the performance of libraries and, in the long term, strengthen the capacity for research in leading library schools, enhance productive collaboration among those schools, and establish the discipline of information studies as the

scientific base for professional education and the management of libraries and archives.

III. The Committee on Information Studies

The CLR Committee on Information Studies will continue to serve the Council and its funding sources in an advisory capacity, both during the period of program development and subsequently as operations get under way. It is anticipated that the Committee will meet with the collaborating library schools and with the Center staff to prepare periodic reviews of progress and to watch for opportunities to be useful to these enterprises over time. Committee membership will continue to be drawn from the CLR Board and the ranks of academic and public leaders.

* * * * *

As one year ends and another begins, we move from months of talking and listening, thinking and planning, to the point of action. A Working Committee on Library Education has been formed and its members have agreed to undertake a difficult assignment in a brief period of time. Discussions have begun in several key places to consider how an Institute for Advanced Information Studies might be brought to life. And the CLR Committee on Information Studies, which helped to shape this general plan, is now being reconstituted to serve as well during the next phase in this evolution of a profession.

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Administrative Notes

We have often remarked that CLR is able to do its work only with the help of many individuals. External reviewers consider most of the proposals that come to us, and typically several special committees and task forces are at work on one assignment or another. Increasingly, we are also turning to more formal advisory bodies to help shape long-range plans for our primary programs.

The Research Library Committee, a group of some twenty-five individuals from academic administration, the scholarly disciplines, and the library profession, is considering (and learning about) the future of research libraries, concentrating on matters that need attention to assure that libraries will continue to be as responsive as possible to the needs of scholars in the context of institutional objectives and available resources. The Council's Committee on Information Studies has helped develop CLR's new programs related to librarianship and professional education and will continue to review and monitor work in this area. Another, related, body in the early stage of development is the Working Committee on Library Education. The initial members are providing advice for what we think will be an important Council program designed to enable library schools to collaborate on a set of new initiatives that are required if professional education is to deal with the increasingly complex demands that librarianship now faces. The most recent addition, the CLR Grants Committee, has been formed to provide a final review of all important applications for support that come to the Council.

All of these groups are, of course, advisory, but they are also influential, both in refining the Council's programs and in enabling the CLR Board and officers to reach decisions on specific proposals. Membership of task forces and CLR advisory committees is recorded elsewhere in this report.

The CLR Board of Directors, which ultimately is responsible for program definition as well as for overseeing program execution, has three new members. **Peter Likins**, president of Lehigh University, has long had an interest in library operations and served on the Committee on Preservation and Access, the predecessor of the present Commission on Preservation and Access. **Basil Stuart-Stubbs**, the first Canadian to serve on the Council's Board, is an important addition, not only because of his experience and professional distinction but because the Council has always opened a number of its

programs to Canadian participation. Mr. Stuart-Stubbs was for many years the director of the University of British Columbia libraries, and for the last decade has been director of the School of Library, Archival and Information Studies at the University of British Columbia. The third new member is Sidney Verba, Carl H. Pforzheimer professor at Harvard University and director of the Harvard University Library. Mr. Verba, who is also a member of the Commission on Preservation and Access, has been involved in many CLR activities and has, since assuming the Harvard librarianship, been an influential and imaginative contributor to national library undertakings. The new members join the twenty present members of the Board to maintain the tradition of leadership and distinction that the Board has reflected since CLR was organized in 1956.

Even as we note new additions to the Council's roster of assistants, we need to record the departure of Deanna Marcum, who, after eight years, initially as program associate and finally as vice president, has left CLR to assume the position of dean of the School of Library and Information Science at The Catholic University of America in Washington. Ms. Marcum has agreed to serve on several of the CLR advisory committees, so her experience will not be lost to us.

Another administrative matter worth mention is a new emphasis on grants management. Many of the proposals funded by CLR, both individual and institutional, tend to underestimate the time required for project completion. Council records are now organized to enable close tracking of grant activity. With the same objective, proposals are being carefully reviewed to identify and correct scheduling difficulties during the review stage.

For the record, it is also noted that the Council and the Commission on Preservation and Access have agreed to continue the host agreement by which the Council provides required staff services to the Commission, thus reducing Commission overhead costs and maintaining an effective relationship between the two organizations.

Finally, we want to acknowledge again the support of the foundations that fund both CLR's operating programs and the new endeavors we undertake from time to time. Foundation support for the Council is amplified many times over by the benefits of CLR support for academic and research libraries and for the professionals who manage the services those libraries provide. During the year covered by this report, funding has been provided by the following foundations.

The Ford Foundation
 The J. Paul Getty Trust
 The William and Flora Hewlett Foundation
 The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation
 The Pew Charitable Trusts
 The Alfred P. Sloan Foundation

Program Guidelines and Grant Application Procedures

The Council on Library Resources supports work by individuals and organizations on matters pertinent to library service and information systems, with the primary objective of improving the quality and performance of academic and research libraries. Individuals with specific interests and expertise are encouraged to take the initiative and propose for consideration projects within the broad areas of the Council's program, as described in this report.

In addition, the Council sponsors several competitive programs, including the CLR Fellows program, the Cooperative Research program, and the Academic Library Management Intern Program. These programs are described in brochures available from CLR.

Application Procedures

Initial inquiries should state the purpose of the proposed work, indicate methodology, establish the credentials of the responsible individuals, and provide an estimate of total costs and funding requirements. CLR will respond promptly with an indication of interest. If subsequent exploration seems justified, preparation of a complete proposal will be suggested. Full documentation should include:

1. A concise description of the proposed project.
2. A thorough explanation of the work to be done, including objectives and methods to be employed. A timetable, pertinent background information, and plans for evaluation of results should also be provided.
3. A detailed budget linking costs to project components.
4. Curricula vitae of the principal investigators.

Proposals are carefully reviewed by CLR staff and, when necessary, external advisors, who consider such matters as relevance to current CLR interests and activities; relationship to other, similar work; projected costs in the context of the work described; and importance of anticipated results. The Council also

looks for evidence of institutional support, including cost sharing. With the exception of a few cyclical programs, there are no submission deadlines.

Support is not provided for construction or renovation, collection acquisitions, routine operating costs, activities judged to be of limited influence, or work that essentially repeats previous research. CLR does not fund indirect costs or, with rare exceptions, equipment purchases. While CLR, in consultation with its advisors, often initiates and promotes work in program areas, exploratory correspondence and conversation are always welcome, and all proposals receive careful consideration.

All inquiries should be addressed to Council on Library Resources, 1785 Massachusetts Avenue, N.W., Suite 313, Washington, D.C. 20036.

ACTIVE PROJECTS

FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

Grants and Contracts Active in Fiscal 1989 (unaudited)

	FY 1989			
	Unpaid 6/30/88	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/89
American Antiquarian Society				
Worcester, Mass.				
Completion of the North American Imprints Program	\$ 15,000	\$ -0-	\$ 15,000	\$ -0-
Association of Research Libraries				
Washington, D.C.				
1989 automation inventory as a management tool	-0-	1,500	1,500	-0-
Institute for library educators Third—1988	25,000	-0-	25,000	-0-
Study of serial costs	-0-	15,000	15,000	-0-
Trudi Bellardo				
Washington, D.C.				
History of online information retrieval systems	100	-0-	-0-	100
The Bridge to China Foundation				
Oakland, Calif.				
Book drive for Chinese universities	-0-	4,516	-0-	4,516
Brigham Young University				
Provo, Utah				
The Conservator, a non-damaging book return unit	-0-	12,500	5,000	7,500
Carnegie Mellon University				
Pittsburgh, Pa.				
Establish a study group on the structure of electronic text	3,000	-0-	3,000	-0-

	FY 1989			
	Unpaid 6/30/88	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/89
Marianna Tax Choldin				
Urbana, Ill.				
Study of Soviet practice of censoring via translation	-0-	5,060	-0-	5,060
Columbia University				
New York, N. Y.				
Empirical study of the overlap between the <i>Avery Index to Architectural Periodicals</i> and the <i>Architectural Periodicals Index</i>	2,990	-0-	2,990	-0-
Library fellows program	24,450	-0-	24,450	-0-
Measuring the public services impact of an online catalog	11,200	-0-	-0-	11,200
Commission on Preservation and Access				
Washington, D.C.				
Establishing the Commission on Preservation and Access as an independent body				
September 1988	-0-	25,000	25,000	-0-
November 1988	-0-	2,017,000	2,017,000	-0-
February 1989	-0-	25,128	25,128	-0-
June 1989	-0-	200,000	50,000	150,000
Cornell University				
Ithaca, N. Y.				
Study of bibliographic databases accessible through the campus network	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
Eckerd College				
St. Petersburg, Fla.				
Survey of academic administrators' views on the role of college libraries	-0-	1,830	1,830	-0-

	FY 1989			
	Unpaid 6/30/88	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/89
Enoch Pratt Free Library				
Baltimore, Md.				
Centennial symposium	1,000	(3,412)	(2,412)	-0-
European Foundation for Library Cooperation				
Brussels, Belgium				
Development funds	1,000	-0-	-0-	1,000
Franklin & Marshall College				
Lancaster, Pa.				
Preservation and collection management at liberal arts college libraries	-0-	2,980	-0-	2,980
George Washington University				
Washington, D.C.				
Assessing the selection and utilization of MEDLINE search systems	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
Harvard University				
Cambridge, Mass.				
Music librarianship in America	-0-	20,000	18,000	2,000
Study of electronic information delivery	-0-	32,500	16,250	16,250
Howard University				
Washington, D.C.				
Mary McLeod Bethune: annotated bibliography with personal recollections	-0-	3,132	3,132	-0-
Illinois State University				
Normal-Bloomington, Ill.				
Unobtrusive testing of reference service in a divisional academic library	-0-	1,800	1,800	-0-

	FY 1989			
	Unpaid 6/30/88	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/89
Indiana University of Pennsylvania				
Indiana, Pa.				
Improving subject access in online public access catalogs	-0-	40,000	15,000	25,000
International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions				
The Hague, Netherlands				
IFLA Fellows program	-0-	125,000	45,000	80,000
Joint colloquium on newspaper resource sharing	11,700	-0-	11,700	-0-
Johns Hopkins University				
Baltimore, Md.				
Knowledge management: expanding the scholarly role of research libraries	-0-	282,808	100,000	182,808
Library of Congress				
Washington, D.C.				
Completion of a series of training videotapes on library preservation	1,110	(1,110)	-0-	-0-
National conference on state preservation programs	-0-	14,375	14,375	-0-
Louisiana State University				
Baton Rouge, La.				
The scope and impact of bookmobile service in the United States	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
Mid-Atlantic Preservation Service				
Bethlehem, Pa.				
Meeting on MAPS building program	-0-	3,550 (650)	3,000 (100)	-0-
Study of microfiche production standards	24,131	-0-	24,131	-0-

	FY 1989			
	Unpaid 6/30/88	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/89
Museum Computer Network				
Syracuse, N. Y.				
Testing the use of MARC formats for cataloging art objects	-0-	20,000	15,000	5,000
National Commission on Libraries and Information Science				
Washington, D.C.				
Invitational conference on information literacy	-0-	20,000	19,000	1,000
National Information Standards Organization				
Gaithersburg, Md.				
Development of an American national standard for hardcover edition bindings	20,700	-0-	-0-	20,700
U.S. representation at an international meeting on paper permanence	2,000	-0-	-0-	2,000
New York Public Library				
New York, N. Y.				
Paper permanency program	-0-	7,500	7,500	-0-
North Carolina State University				
Raleigh, N.C.				
A study of the editing efficiency of an online bibliographic information system	-0-	2,350	2,350	-0-
Oberlin College				
Oberlin, Ohio				
Survey of liberal arts college libraries to document research and education support in the sciences	-0-	1,924	1,924	-0-

	FY 1989			
	Unpaid 6/30/88	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/89
OCLC Online Computer Library Center Dublin, Ohio				
Increase accessibility of Library of Congress subject headings in online bibliographic systems	63,700	-0-	60,000	3,700
Pennsylvania State University University Park, Pa.				
Study of user needs in the field of speech communication	2,968	-0-	2,968	-0-
The Research Libraries Group, Inc. Stanford, Calif.				
Creation of a national database of public records information	532	(532)	-0-	-0-
Hans Rütimann New York, N.Y.				
Development of an international bibliographic records database on preservation activity	50,000	-0-	50,000	-0-
Rutgers University New Brunswick, N.J.				
Impact of interdisciplinary research on library collection building	-0-	3,000	-0-	3,000
Simmons College Boston, Mass.				
Symposium on solutions to the problems of recruiting, educating, and training cataloging librarians	15,000	2,800	16,500	1,300
Stanford University Stanford, Calif.				
Economic analysis of scholarly periodical costs	-0-	27,800	-0-	27,800

	FY 1989			
	Unpaid 6/30/88	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/89
State University of New York				
Albany, N.Y.				
To publish the proceedings of an international conference on classification in the computer age	2,000	-0-	2,000	-0-
Abigail Dahl-Hansen Studdiford				
Bridgewater, N.J.				
Study of public policy issues relating to research libraries	8,000	(8,000)	-0-	-0-
Syracuse University				
Syracuse, N.Y.				
Textual analysis of information needs derived from abstracts of documents	1,913	-0-	-0-	1,913
Trinity University				
San Antonio, Tex.				
Collection growth and automation in academic libraries	-0-	2,000	2,000	-0-
University of Alabama				
Tuscaloosa, Ala.				
Book on library education	-0-	8,300	2,500	5,800
Pilot study for an online bibliographical reference database for simulation/gaming	-0-	2,986	-0-	2,986
University of Alberta				
Edmonton, Alberta, Canada				
Regional resource sharing program	-0-	3,000	-0-	3,000
University of California				
Berkeley, Calif.				
A test of measures and correlates of academic library performance	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-

	FY 1989			
	Unpaid 6/30/88	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/89
University of California				
Los Angeles, Calif.				
Conference on conceptual foundations of cataloging	3,670	(1,070)	2,600	-0-
Research program: long-range strategic planning for libraries and information resources in research universities	350,000	-0-	180,859	169,141
Senior fellows conference—1988	25,000	-0-	20,000	5,000
Senior fellows program—1989	30,000	-0-	-0-	30,000
Study of microcomputer-based digital imaging as a technique for preservation of library materials	2,500	-0-	-0-	2,500
University of Chicago				
Chicago, Ill.				
Multi-institutional professional development program for recent library school graduates	12,221	-0-	12,221	-0-
University of Georgia				
Athens, Ga.				
Internships for recent library school graduates	53,581	-0-	17,073	36,508
University of Hawaii, Manoa				
Honolulu, Hawaii				
To study users of full-text databases	2,988	-0-	2,988	-0-
University of Illinois				
Chicago, Ill.				
Study of humanists' use of libraries	-0-	23,000	23,000	-0-
Study of strategic planning issues for the research university	40,200	-0-	40,200	-0-

	FY 1989			
	Unpaid 6/30/88	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/89
University of Illinois				
Urbana, Ill.				
1988 Allerton Institute	5,000	(786)	4,214	-0-
Application of behavioral research methodology to environmental design problems in libraries	-0-	2,587	2,587	-0-
Developing and evaluating online catalog interface enhancements	8,000	-0-	6,000	2,000
Study of perceived values of advanced subject degrees	3,000	-0-	3,000	-0-
University of Kentucky				
Lexington, Ky.				
Revision of the <i>Guide to the Library of Congress Classification</i>	-0-	3,000	-0-	3,000
University of Louisville				
Louisville, Ky.				
Methods used to limit use of medical literature proven invalid and retracted	-0-	2,778	2,778	-0-
University of Maryland				
College Park, Md.				
Anglo-American cataloging rules as a knowledge base	-0-	7,113	6,500	613
Improved bibliographic instruction for periodical literature	-0-	2,900	2,900	-0-
University of Michigan				
Ann Arbor, Mich.				
Increase accessibility of Library of Congress subject headings in online bibliographic systems	22,925	-0-	20,000	2,925
Second European Conference on Archives	10,000	-0-	5,000	5,000

	FY 1989			
	Unpaid 6/30/88	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/89
University of Minnesota				
St. Paul, Minn.				
Plan and design a model academic integrated information center	17,000	-0-	17,000	-0-
University of Missouri				
Columbia, Mo.				
Internships for recent library school graduates	37,392	(21,454)	15,938	-0-
Study of information needs of philosophers	34,625	-0-	32,000	2,625
University of North Carolina				
Chapel Hill, N.C.				
Study of the Regional Depository Library System	3,000	-0-	3,000	-0-
University of Pittsburgh				
Pittsburgh, Pa.				
An advanced institute for government archivists	-0-	60,676	20,000	40,676
University of Toronto				
Toronto, Ontario, Canada				
Information retrieval systems and their users	-0-	80,000	40,000	40,000
University of Western Ontario				
London, Ontario, Canada				
Study of bibliographic and text-linguistic schemata in the user-intermediary interaction	500	-0-	500	-0-
University of Wisconsin				
Madison, Wis.				
Measurement and evaluation of library reference service	-0-	5,605	-0-	5,605
Symposium on <i>The 21st Century and the Future of the Book</i>	-0-	2,825	2,825	-0-

	FY 1989			
	Unpaid 6/30/88	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/89
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University Blacksburg, Va.				
Comparison of advanced retrieval approaches for online catalog access	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
Yale University New Haven, Conn.				
Training support for the institution of self-managing teams within technical services	-0-	27,400	25,000	2,400
Undergraduate Internship Program	1,000	(940)	60	-0-
Other refunds and adjustments from prior years' grants and contracts	-0-	(5,222)	(5,222)	-0-
Totals	\$950,096	\$3,168,223 (43,176)	\$3,168,271 (7,734)	\$914,606

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Report of Independent Accountants

August 21, 1989

To the Board of Directors of
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

In our opinion, the accompanying balance sheets and the related statements of revenues, expenses and changes in fund balance, of cash flows and of functional expenses present fairly, in all material respects, the financial position of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1989 and 1988, and the results of its operations and its functional expenses for the year ended June 30, 1989 and its cash flows for the two years then ended in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles. These financial statements are the responsibility of the Council's management; our responsibility is to express an opinion on these financial statements based on our audits. We conducted our audits of these statements in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards which require that we plan and perform the audit to obtain reasonable assurance about whether the financial statements are free of material misstatement. An audit includes examining, on a test basis, evidence supporting the amounts and disclosures in the financial statements, assessing the accounting principles used and significant estimates made by management, and evaluating the overall financial statement presentation. We believe that our audits provide a reasonable basis for the opinion expressed above.

Price Waterhouse
Washington, D.C.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Balance Sheets

	<u>June 30</u>	
	<u>1989</u>	<u>1988</u>
ASSETS		
Cash and cash equivalents (Note 2)	\$ 457,059	\$6,527,756
Short-term investments (Note 2)	3,083,300	
Grants receivable (Note 2)		
Unrestricted	900,000	1,200,000
Restricted	837,160	1,390,500
Other assets	<u>115,549</u>	<u>13,228</u>
Total assets	<u>\$5,393,068</u>	<u>\$9,131,484</u>
LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE		
Deferred revenue (Note 2)		
Unrestricted	\$ 900,000	\$1,500,000
Restricted	1,046,416	3,900,419
Grants and contracts payable (Note 2)		
Unrestricted	305,836	125,066
Restricted	608,770	825,030
Accounts payable and accrued employee benefits	<u>54,812</u>	<u>76,790</u>
Total liabilities	<u>2,915,834</u>	<u>6,427,305</u>
Fund balance		
Appropriated	372,670	602,302
Unappropriated	<u>2,104,564</u>	<u>2,101,877</u>
Total fund balance	<u>2,477,234</u>	<u>2,704,179</u>
Total liabilities and fund balance	<u>\$5,393,068</u>	<u>\$9,131,484</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Statement of Revenues, Expenses and Changes in Fund Balance

FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1989
(With Comparative Totals for 1988)

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Restricted</u>	<u>Total 1989</u>	<u>Total 1988</u>
Revenues (Note 2)				
Grants and contracts	\$ 600,000	\$2,600,177	\$3,200,177	\$1,305,238
Contributions		259,578	259,578	139,062
Interest	<u>372,975</u>		<u>372,975</u>	<u>308,584</u>
Total revenues	<u>972,975</u>	<u>2,859,755</u>	<u>3,832,730</u>	<u>1,752,884</u>
Expenses (Notes 2, 3 and 4)				
Program				
Research	13,732	620,732	634,464	356,312
Access	35,151	250,044	285,195	146,443
Bibliography	123,434		123,434	141,682
Librarianship	465,112	36,759	501,871	130,938
Library Resources and Preservation	<u>309,796</u>	<u>1,952,220</u>	<u>2,262,016</u>	<u>490,604</u>
Total program	947,225	2,859,755	3,806,980	1,265,979
Administration	<u>252,695</u>		<u>252,695</u>	<u>234,853</u>
Total expenses	<u>1,199,920</u>	<u>2,859,755</u>	<u>4,059,675</u>	<u>1,500,832</u>
(Deficit) excess of revenues over expenses	(226,945)		(226,945)	252,052
Fund balance, begin- ning of year	<u>2,704,179</u>		<u>2,704,179</u>	<u>2,452,127</u>
Fund balance, end of year	<u>\$2,477,234</u>	<u>\$ —</u>	<u>\$2,477,234</u>	<u>\$2,704,179</u>

Statements of Cash Flows

	<u>Year ended June 30</u>	
	<u>1989</u>	<u>1988</u>
Cash flows from operating activities:		
(Deficit) excess of revenues over expenses	\$ (226,945)	\$ 252,052
Adjustments to reconcile (deficit) excess of revenue over expenses to net cash (used in) provided by operating activities:		
Amortization of investment discounts	15,145	
Decrease in grants receivable	853,340	1,592,664
Increase in other assets	(102,321)	(753)
(Decrease) increase in deferred revenue	(3,454,003)	599,806
(Decrease) increase in accounts payable and accrued employee benefits	(21,978)	16,204
(Decrease) increase in grants and contracts payable	<u>(35,490)</u>	<u>(289,319)</u>
Total adjustments	<u>(2,745,307)</u>	<u>1,918,602</u>
Net cash (used in) provided by operating activities	(2,972,252)	2,170,654
Cash flows from investing activities:		
Purchase of short-term investments	(3,496,851)	
Sale of short-term investments	<u>398,406</u>	
Net cash used in investing activities	<u>(3,098,445)</u>	<u>—</u>
Net (decrease) increase in cash and cash equivalents	(6,070,697)	2,170,654
Cash and cash equivalents, beginning of year	<u>6,527,756</u>	<u>4,357,102</u>
Cash and cash equivalents, end of year	<u>\$ 457,059</u>	<u>\$6,527,756</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

**STATEMENT OF FUNCTIONAL EXPENSES
FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1989**

(With Comparative Totals for 1988)

	Research	Access	Bibliography	Librarianship	Library Resources and Preservation	Total Program	Administration	Year ended June 30	
								1989	1988
Unrestricted									
Grants and contracts		\$ 10,937	\$ 2,350	\$136,100	\$ 302,833	\$ 452,220		\$ 452,220	\$ 130,583
Refunds and overappropriations		(116)	(1,069)	(940)	(2,546)	(4,671)		(4,671)	(30,608)
Staff and travel	\$ 3,810	12,867	15,536	78,939	7,773	118,925	\$129,039	247,964	241,635
Advisory committees, consultants and interns	918		9,555	129,755	1,736	141,964		141,964	49,584
Board expenses							25,092	25,092	23,528
Office expenses			77,972	6,716		84,688	8,669	93,357	12,727
Support services	9,004	11,463	19,090	114,542		154,099	89,895	243,994	229,083
	<u>13,732</u>	<u>35,151</u>	<u>123,434</u>	<u>465,112</u>	<u>309,796</u>	<u>947,225</u>	<u>252,695</u>	<u>1,199,920</u>	<u>656,532</u>
Restricted									
Grants and contracts	488,838	214,269		60,676	1,952,220	2,716,003		2,716,003	261,226
Refunds and overappropriations	(8,000)	(5,016)		(25,489)		(38,505)		(38,505)	(37,110)
Staff and travel	54,809	7,220				62,029		62,029	371,120
Advisory committees, consultants and interns	36,449	25,304				61,753		61,753	74,398
Office expenses	369	640		1,572		2,581		2,581	34,287
Support services	48,267	7,627				55,894		55,894	140,379
	<u>620,732</u>	<u>250,044</u>		<u>36,759</u>	<u>1,952,220</u>	<u>2,859,755</u>		<u>2,859,755</u>	<u>844,300</u>
Total expenses	<u>\$634,464</u>	<u>\$285,195</u>	<u>\$123,434</u>	<u>\$501,871</u>	<u>\$2,262,016</u>	<u>\$3,806,980</u>	<u>\$252,695</u>	<u>\$4,059,675</u>	<u>\$1,500,832</u>

Notes to Financial Statements

JUNE 30, 1989 AND 1988

Note 1—Organization

The Council on Library Resources, Inc. (Council) is a non-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1956 for the purpose of promoting library research. The Council, a private operating foundation, is exempt from Federal income tax under Internal Revenue Code section 501(c)(3).

The Council's operations are financed through unrestricted general support grants and through several restricted grants from private foundations and other sources. The Council conducts its work through directly administered projects as well as grants to and contracts with other organizations or individuals.

Note 2—Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

The Council's financial statements have been prepared on the accrual basis of accounting except for the costs of office furniture and equipment which are consistently charged to expense when incurred. The Council does not consider such expenditures to be material to warrant capitalization and depreciation. The significant accounting policies followed in the preparation of the financial statements are described below.

Grants

Grants to the Council are recorded as receivables and deferred revenue when the Council is notified that it has been awarded the funds. Unrestricted grant revenue is recognized as income in accordance with the budgeted annual payments specified by the grantors. Restricted grant revenue is recognized when the related expenses are incurred.

Grant and contract expenses are recorded when the recipients are notified that they are to receive the funds. Current period expenses are reduced for grant refunds and overappropriations.

Contributions

Various universities made restricted contributions to the Council to support the preservation program in fiscal years 1987 and 1988. These and other contributions to fund this program were recorded as deferred revenue when received. Contribution revenue is recognized when the related expenses are incurred. These contributions and certain deferred grants, which totalled \$2,067,000, were recognized as revenue and expenses in fiscal year 1989 when they were granted to the Commission on Preservation and Access (Commission), a newly formed entity.

Cash and cash equivalents, and short-term investments

Cash and cash equivalents, which primarily consist of deposits in a money market fund, and short-term investments, which consist of treasury notes, are recorded at

cost which approximates market. These balances include restricted amounts of \$818,026 and \$3,334,949 at June 30, 1989 and 1988, respectively. Cash equivalents represent investments with original maturities of 90 days or less. Interest is not restricted by the related grants and accordingly is recognized as unrestricted revenue.

Functional allocation of expenses

Costs of providing the various programs have been summarized on a functional basis in the accompanying financial statements. Certain indirect costs identified as support services costs have been allocated to programs and administration on a systematic basis. These costs primarily include salary, benefits, rent and other expenses.

Note 3—Retirement Plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council's defined contribution retirement annuity program administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the plan provide for full and immediate vesting of both the Council's and employees' contributions. The Council's contribution, net of that reimbursed by the Commission, was approximately \$53,000 and \$84,000 for fiscal years 1989 and 1988, respectively.

Note 4—Commitments

The Council entered into a lease agreement for office space expiring in 1990. The minimum future rental will be approximately \$140,000 for the remaining year. As part of this lease agreement, the Council will continue to be assessed an annual charge based on its proportionate share of the increase in the operating costs of the building. For the years ended June 30, 1989 and 1988, rent expense totaled \$136,000 and \$133,000, respectively, of which approximately \$23,000 and \$21,000, respectively, represents the Council's share of the increase in the operating costs.

The Council subleases a portion of its leased office space. Rental income from this sublease amounted to approximately \$35,000 in each of fiscal years 1989 and 1988.

Note 5—Related Party

The Council entered into an agreement with the Commission effective July 1, 1988 under which the Council provides office space, employee services, equipment, supplies and other overhead items to the Commission. Commission staff members are employees of the Council and receive the same benefits as members of the Council. The percentage of shared overhead costs charged to the Commission is negotiated annually. For fiscal year 1989, the Commission's share was 25%.

Certain members of the Council's Board of Directors are also members of the Commission's Board of Directors. However, as these members are in the minority and there are no other elements of managerial or financial control, these two entities have not been consolidated.

Index

- Academic Library Management Intern Program, 20, 42
- Albright, Elaine, 23
- Alfred P. Sloan Foundation, 41
- Anderson, Rachael, 23
- Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, 41
- Association of Research Libraries, 12, 14
- Bader, Shelley A., 21
- Bertram, Sheila, 22
- Bibliographic Services Study Committee, 13, 16, 33
- Boyce, Judith, 21
- Boyce, Bert, 21
- Bridge to China Foundation, 18
- Brigham Young University, 15
- Bunting, Alison, 23
- Center for Advanced Information Studies, 29, 30, 31
- Chan, Lois M., 17
- Choldin, Marianna Tax, 20
- CLR Fellows Program, 18, 20, 42
- Commission on Preservation and Access, 12, 13, 15, 41
- Committee on Information Studies, 29, 32, 33, 40
- Cooperative Research program, 18, 21, 42
- Cornell University, 21
- Crookall, David, 22
- Currie, Jean, 21
- Distad, Merrill, 22
- Eckerd College, 21
- Edelman, Hendrik, 22
- Edgerton, Janet, 22
- Elzy, Cheryl, 21
- Faculty/Librarian Cooperative Research program, 18, 21, 42
- Ford Foundation, 17, 41
- Foundation Library Committee, 13
- Fox, Edward, 22
- Franklin & Marshall College, 16
- George Washington University, 21
- Grants Committee, 35, 40
- Harbin, Larry, 22
- Hardesty, Larry, 21
- Harvard University, 15
- Hayes, Robert, 13
- Horres, Mary, 23
- Iannuzzi, Patricia, 21
- IFLA Fellows, 23
- Illinois State University, 21
- Indiana University, 21
- Indiana University of Pennsylvania, 17
- Information Studies Collaborative, 29, 30, 31
- Institute for Government Archivists, 24
- International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, 23
- J. Paul Getty Trust, 41
- Jeng, Ling Hwey, 20
- Johns Hopkins University, 14, 15
- Johnson, Edward, 23
- Kaser, David, 21
- Koepp, Donald, 21
- Lancaster, Wilfrid, 21
- Library of Congress, 16
- Likins, Peter, 40
- Linked Systems Project, 13, 16, 33–34
- Louisiana State University, 21
- Marcum, Deanna, 41
- Mid-Atlantic Preservation Service, 16
- Montanelli, Dale, 22
- Museum Computer Network, 17
- National Commission on Libraries and Information Science, 18
- National Coordinated Cataloging Program, 13, 16
- National Science Foundation, 14
- Neuman, Delia, 22
- New York Public Library, 16
- North Carolina State University, 22
- Nourie, Alan, 21
- Oberlin College, 22
- OCLC Online Computer Library Center, 12
- Patterson, Robert, 23
- Pew Charitable Trusts, 41
- Pfeifer, Mark, 22
- Phipps, Shelley, 23
- Piemme, Thomas E., 21
- Potthoff, Joy, 22
- Princeton University, 21
- Pritchard, Sarah M., 21
- Reid, Marion, 23
- Research Libraries Group, 12
- Research Library Committee, 12, 13, 14, 23, 34, 40
- Ricker, Alison Scott, 22
- Riggs, Donald, 23
- Robbins, Jane, 23
- Robert Vosper IFLA Fellows, 23
- Roosa, Mark, 23
- Rosenthal, Joseph, 21
- Rutgers University, 22

- Ruus, Laine, 23
Schmidt, Sherrie, 23
Science and Engineering Indicators, 14
Senior Fellows, 23
Simmons College, 24
Sims-Wood, Janet, 20
Snodgrass, Gwendolyn, 22
Spaulding, Helen, 23
Stanford University, 15
State Library of Louisiana, 21
Stevens, Norman, 21
Stewart, Linda, 21
Stieg, Margaret F., 24
Stuart-Stubbs, Basil, 40
Taylor, Raymond, 22
UCLA Senior Fellows, 23
University of Alabama, 22, 24
University of Alberta, 22
University of California, Berkeley, 21, 22
University of California, Los Angeles, 13, 23
University of Connecticut, 21
University of Illinois at Chicago, 14, 15
University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, 21, 22
University of Kentucky, 17
University of Louisville, 22
University of Maryland, 22
University of Minnesota, 13
University of Pittsburgh, 24
University of Toronto, 17
University of Wisconsin-Madison, 15, 18
Van Campen, Rebecca, 22
Van House, Nancy, 22
Verba, Sidney, 41
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, 22
Vosper, Robert, 23
Walckiers, Marc, 23
Watstein, Sarah B., 21
Weil, Beth, 22
Welch Medical Library, 14, 15
Wellheiser, Joanna, 23
Werking, Richard Hume, 20, 23
William and Flora Hewlett Foundation, 41
Wilson, Florence, 23
Wilson, Linda, 22
Wilson, Myoung Chung, 22
Witmer, Jeffrey, 22
Wittenborg, Karin, 23
Working Committee on Library Education, 29, 30, 32, 35, 40
Yale University, 15
Yarbrough, Paul, 21

